

Some Amplifier Circuits for Discrete Photodetectors

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ABSTRACT

Photodetectors are the key element of many sensors and have the task of converting optical information into readable electrical information. The electronic amplifier, at least the first stage, is the second essential element of such a sensor, without which the photodetector cannot work. Although technological progress offers more and more integrated solutions, discrete solutions are still relevant for research and development, especially at low cost. We summarise some results from projects that cannot be mentioned in detail for reasons of confidentiality.

KEYWORDS: photodetector, electronic amplifier, photodiode (PD), avalanche photodiode (APD), silicon photo multiplier (SiPM), photo multiplier (PMT)

INTRODUCTION

A first interesting expanding application area is visible light communication (VLC). The increasing need for bandwidth on the one hand and the demand for private communication on the other could drive the adoption of this technology in the next decade, which can already reach speeds of up to 1 Gbps. VLC requires line of sight, especially at high speeds, which can be a weakness but also a strength (privacy). IoT devices are an interesting application area for low-cost, low-speed solutions, still to be explored.

A second interesting area of application is the extraction of information from optical signals of different wavelengths with a very high dynamic range of more than 100 dB (five decades and more). Applications of this kind can be found in medicine (e.g. tissue analysis) and material science (material analysis). Very strong and very weak signals can alternate in short time intervals. In this area, too, there is a need for effective, low-cost solutions to achieve broad market penetration.

CONCEPT

In the field of visible light communication, a cheap photodiode can be used as a receiver and an existing LED or LED-array, whose main task is in fact illumination, as a transmitter. In this way, the additional costs for the system are low. A relatively small modulated external signal superimposed with high optical internal power, high ambient light intensity and interference must be recovered and demodulated into a bit stream. Bidirectional communication can be established, for example between luminaires. Measuring the signal intensity can provide information about the distance between the devices. Based on the received digital (bit stream) and analogue (intensity of the signal) information, various reactions can be programmed.

In the second area, the measurement of tissue or material parameters, a sensor capable of detecting very high and very small signals should be used. On the one hand, the photodetector must have a high dynamic range, high sensitivity and low noise. An avalanche photodiode (APD) or a silicon photomultiplier (SiPM) is a good compromise between performance and price. A photomultiplier (PMT) could also be used, but it is generally very expensive, bulky and fragile. On the other hand, the electronic amplifier needs a special structure and topology to do the job. A logarithmic characteristic of the amplifier should be used. In the analogue world, this can be achieved with a semiconductor pn junction, which has an exponential dependence of current on voltage. Disadvantages are the bandwidth of the measurements and the necessary additional averaging at very low signals. Temperature compensation is also an issue to be addressed.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In the first application area, a transimpedance amplifier with an AC coupling was used. This enables direct filtering of the ambient light without having to subtract it. In this way, the dynamic range of the receiver circuit is completely used only for decoding the superimposed modulated bit stream. Compensation of the offset currents is a good practice to improve the results. Subsequent stages, including filters, amplifiers and a phase-locked loop (PLL), are required to demodulate the FSK (frequency shift keying) signals and estimate the signal strength as a measure of distance. The modulation of the information can be achieved in several ways: a sine or square wave of a specific frequency can be superimposed to the DC bias of the LED. Alternatively an on/off keying (OOK) of the LED can be used. The modulation should not be seen by the eye and adapted to the current level of dimming of the LED. The standards for optical flicker have also to be complied.

In the second case, logarithmic transimpedance amplifiers in combination with an APD are a good choice. This allows a wide dynamic range and high sensitivity. The disadvantage is the limited bandwidth when the

signals have a very low intensity. Averaging time is required to reconstruct the signal. Temperature stabilization is to be implemented, due to the strong temperature dependence of the APDs. Proper position of the photodetector, electromagnetic shielding and proper layout of the electronics circuit are also to be implemented, due to the high sensitivity of the system. This technique makes it possible, for example, to measure tissue parameters at a depth of several centimeters. The detection of material properties can be evaluated based on the exponential decay of the emitted light after a short excitation pulse.

Figure 1: (a) amplifier with ac coupling (b) logarithmic amplifier

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A system of cheap devices, which communicate through VLC, could be realized. Distances up to 20 m are possible. A simple but effective swarm behavior, based on a small set of commands and the measurement of the distance between devices was implemented. The potential of these solution is still to be explored: for example we see in Switzerland increasing cases of intelligence city illumination, which rely on expensive radio or radar solutions. The developed system could reach similar goals in a much cheaper way. Further applications could be envisioned. A research device for the measurement of deep tissue parameters could be implemented. A simplified version of this solution will be implemented in a product by a start-up company.

Figure 2: a) test field with VLC luminaries b) 8-channel APD module with logarithmic amplifiers

CONCLUSIONS

In many research and development application fields discrete photodetectors and their amplifier circuits play a decisive role. The main families of discrete photodetectors (PD, APD, SiPM, PMT) can be combined with different kinds of electronic amplifiers in order to cope with the desired task.

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REFERENCES

- [1] R. Grabher, G. Piai, "Lighting System Based on Visible Light Communication", LED Professional Symposium 2018 (LpS 2018), Proceedings, Bregenz (AT), S. 338-345
- [2] P. C. Hobbs, "Building Electro-Optical Systems: Making It All Work", Wiley, 2022

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